

INTERVIEW QUESTIONS RELATED TO COGNITIVE DIMENSIONS - FOR USER STUDY "MAINTAINING HIERARCHICAL CONTROL APPLICATIONS WITH 4DIAC IDE"

Interviewee: _____ **Date:** _____

Interviewer: _____

The application was hierarchically structured with subapplications. Did this hierarchy hinder your understanding of the application? Does it have advantages? (Abstraction)

How did you like the capabilities to restructure the application and did you experience any problems with that (Viscosity)?

Did you open multiple editor tabs/windows at the same time? Do you prefer using multiple windows or navigating through an application within a single editor tab (Visibility)?

Did you find the information you needed easily, for example via the properties view, the outline, or via tooltips (Visibility)?

Did you modify any block types? If yes, how did you like this feature? If no, why not (Premature Commitment)?

Were you aware of the context of the application parts that you worked on (Hidden Dependencies)?

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Did you experience any problems with the used terminology, i.e., naming of displayed content (Abstraction) and/or icons used?

Did you experience any inconsistencies (Consistency)? Where?

Did you find any items/views you thought are unnecessary or unnecessarily complex (Diffuseness)? Where?

Did you miss a specific tool feature, e.g., a particular view or editor? Do you have any other comments?
